

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B246
Date: 22 September 2006
Take Off 09:32:57Z
Landing: 14:42:00Z
Flight Time 5h09m03s

Campaign: ICEPIC

Operating Area: South West

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
8	Familiarisation	Rachel Murray	Directflight
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Flight Track:

B246 Track 22-SEP-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b246
 Date: 22 Sept 2006
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: South West

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
091806		INU	0.56 kft	128	To Navigate
091826		Start-Up	0.56 kft	128	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093257		T/O	1.3 kft	271	Cranfield
095401		Video	15.8 kft	248	Start DFC & RFC
100849	102058	Profile 1	16.0 - 4.4 kft	251	1000fpm
102242	102653	Profile 1	4.4 - 0.55 kft	092	4k-250', Q1004
102846	103859	Run 1	0.74 - 0.80 kft	241	500'
103526		Heimann	0.79 kft	230	Cal, 12-18C
104004	105004	Run 2	1.8 kft	234	1500'
105005	105720	Profile 2	1.8 - 8.5 kft	232	1000fpm from 1.5k'
110015		Nevzorov	8.5 kft	153	TWC=70C, LWC=70C
110316	110522	Run 3	8.5 kft	146	Cloud field 1
110912	111204	Run 4	9.5 kft	003	
111444	111648	Run 5	10.5 kft	105	
111826	112020	Run 6	11.6 - 11.5 kft	223	
112204	112436	Run 7.1	13.0 kft	031	
112603		Video	13.0 kft	183	Change Tapes
112713	112904	Run 7.2	13.0 kft	233	
113014		Nevzorov	11.7 kft	298	TWC Alarm On
113706	114305	Run 8	8.5 kft	015	Cloud field 2
114453	114755	Run 9	10.5 kft	228	
115011	115203	Run 10	12.0 kft	093	
115532	115856	Run 11	13.0 kft	300	T Probe iced up
120217		Event	12.2 kft	145	De-ice Turb Probe
121022	121152	Run 12	8.5 kft	064	R12
121350	121632	Run 13	10.0 kft	297	Cloud field 3
122051	122415	Run 14	11.5 kft	071	
122803	123105	Run 15	13.0 kft	245	
123502	123801	Run 16	14.0 kft	070	T Probe iced up
123908		Event	12.6 kft	144	De-ice T. Prboe
124737	125010	Run 17	8.5 - 8.6 kft	161	Cloud field 4
125340	125602	Run 18	9.5 kft	343	
125631		Video	9.9 kft	038	Change Tapes
125928	130218	Run 19	11.0 kft	189	
130515	130654	Run 20	8.6 - 8.5 kft	171	Cloud field 5
131029	131326	Run 21	10.0 kft	350	
131713	131958	Run 22	11.5 kft	175	
132334	132603	Run 23	13.5 kft	354	
132603	133720	Profile 3	13.5 - 3.3 kft	345	1000fpm to 3k'
133905	134253	Profile 3	3.3 - 0.59 kft	102	3k-250', Q1001
134326	135328	Run 24	0.82 - 0.83 kft	111	500'
135004		Heimann	0.82 kft	097	Cal 12-18C
135329	140253	Profile 4	0.83 - 10.0 kft	097	1000fpm from 500'
142943		Video	10.0 kft	068	End of Tapes
144200		Land	0.58 kft	210	Cranfield
144553		Shutdown	0.56 kft	308	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B246 Track 22-SEP-06

Flight No: B246

Date: 21st Sept 2006

Trial objectives:

To investigate the development of ice-phase and precipitation in Cu over the UK.

Location:

In developing Cu clouds over SW / Central S.England (Area Alpha).

Weather:

Either individual, or groups of Cu cloud forming predominantly over land. Evolving clouds may also be tracked over the sea.

Special requirements:

Key temperature levels for cloud penetrations are 0, -3, -6, -9C then colder as reqd. Chilbolton radar not expected to be operating (but may relay range/bearing of target clouds to “Radsearch”, 130.575 MHz). Continuously monitor **turbulence probe** differential pressures – if any icing observed, descend below freezing level to clear. **Nevezorov TWC** – operate at both normal and high temperatures (one cloud at a time).

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Cranfield at 10:00L.
2. Transit to the operating region at FL200 and identify suitable clouds (40mins).
3. Perform profile descent from FL200 to minimum permitted altitude at 1000ft/minute (70mins). May be stepped to avoid cloud penetrations. Profile ideally finishes below target clouds.
4. Perform a SLR below cloud for 10minutes in a direction determined by the mission scientist to remain in inflow of target clouds (85mins).
5. Turn onto reciprocal heading and perform a SLR at 500ft below cloudbase for ten minutes (100mins).
6. Ascend to around the 0C level or 500ft below the cloud top (110mins).
7. Perform a penetration with wings level through the cloud (115mins).
8. If a single cloud is large and clearly identifiable and the cloud is continuing to develop, make a reciprocal turn while ascending by ~1000ft (-3C in temperature) and repeat the cloud penetration several times (150mins).
9. If the cloud is not large or discrete, then proceed successively to the next visible cumulus cell, and repeat the penetrations at approximately 0C for a 10minute interval. Perform reciprocal turn while climbing by intervals of -3C and repeat 10minute runs (150mins).
10. Continue 8 and/or 9 as time permits (250mins).
11. Finish with a profile ascent from minimum permitted altitude to FL200 or 1000ft above highest cumulus tops (whichever is higher) at 1000ft/min.
12. Transit to Cranfield and land (300mins).

Note) – target clouds should be continuing to develop – look for rising cloud tops and solid, sharp-edged cloud boundaries. If red echoes show on the aircraft radar, or cloud top is decreasing, or cloud becomes heavily glaciated (diffuse boundaries) then move on to next cloud

Flight details

Transit via Daventry corridor to the Bristol Channel. Profile descent from ~FL160 on roughly E-W orientation to a point just W of Hartland Point. Bottom part of profile did not appear very well-mixed and lowest cloud was scattered at various levels. Two 10 min legs flown at 500ft amsl and 1500ft amsl. The lowest was probably within the surface mixed layer. Both of these runs were heading SW into the region just N and W of Lands End. Extensive upper cloud over the SW Peninsula was hindering the development of cumulus over land so it was decided to sample shower clouds further to the west over the sea – these were clearly visible on the radar prior to the flight and expected to persist throughout the day.

In total, 5 “cloud regions” were sampled during the flight. The first 3 were more to the W of Lands End and in multi-cellular clusters. Initial penetrations were at 8500ft (roughly the freezing level) and of cells just growing through this altitude at the upwind side of the cluster. Run orientations varied but were generally so as to penetrate these new, growing cells, whilst avoiding too much of the more well-developed part of each cluster (with red echoes typically present on the a/c weather radar).

In each cluster, there were typically 4-5 penetrations, starting at the freezing level and ascending by between 1000 and 2000ft between each run. Typical temperatures sampled were around 0, -3, -6, -9 and -11C. The turbulence probe would regularly ice up during the -11C passes so this would terminate work on this cloud in order to descend below the freezing level. Cloud Phys noted the appearance of many columns/needles during a couple of the -9C passes, indicating possible activity of the Hallett-Mossop process. Highest cloud tops were ascending well above the highest flight level (13000ft, ~4km) to possible 20000ft or so. At this point the clouds showed distinct anvils. Peak updraughts were estimated to be ~8m/s.

Track plots suggest that the 3rd cloud cluster may actually have been two separate ones with the initial runs performed in one and later ones in a second further to the N. The state of evolution of these cloud clusters was similar, such that they could easily be confused visually when turning between successive cloud penetrations.

Later in the flight after about 1100Z, the upper cirrus had moved away, allowing more convection to develop over Cornwall. Some of this cloud appeared to be advected off the coast and develop further. Two sets of cloud penetrations were made in this area off the N.Coast of Cornwall – subsequent analysis of visible satellite images suggest these may have been in a line extending downwind from the Lizard. These cells were more isolated and not extensive in altitude, with minimum cloud top temperatures not much colder than about -11C. It was clear, however, that raindrops were present during the initial penetrations at the freezing level.

Most instruments appeared to function OK. The forward-facing video was indistinct due to degradation of its window but this was recorded for most of the flight. The Nevzorov TWC alarm light came on after the 1st cloud cluster so it was not possible to examine the impact of operating it at different temperatures. Post-flight examination suggested that there were no problems with the vane itself.

~ 4h 45
est.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

P
BROWN

Flight No **B. 246**
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Date 22/9/06

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0831					T/O Cranfield
/					a few Cu 1100ft. 8/8 med/high cloud above.
0946		10000			Newz looks ok at this pt. Oul g/w -1.6 at 10000ft.
/					Video near e down, as
/					FFC is too messy & Southwestered.
1004		16000			Just approaching Newport ☺ Start of profile probably in cloud.
100849		16000	252	ST 24.0 312.0	Start P 171°/16ms ⁻¹
/		8600	QNH		0°C (about 7800 on 1000).
/		Upper Some 1000	cloud finishes good clouds		just west of Lundy. Can see over NE Cornwall
102058		4000			804 QNH 1004
102053		250			
102846		500	241	ST 12.0 40.0	Start R1
1033		upper	cloud		B.L. is not well mixed, extends well to west
103859		"			End R1 continue west
104004		1500			R2 Start, BL looks more well mixed during climb.
/		1500			but can see slight stable layer in haze below
104738		"			Pass warm rain from cluster just down R side. 2 photos. Tops may not be above freezing level.
105005		1500			End 2 e P2

1b

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 246**

Date **22/9/06**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
105728		8500			End P2
110347					In cloud. 2 cells seen in the second.
					Looks like a typical multicell system with cells growing on upwind side.
110953		9500			In 0.
111444		10500		-5	R5 now running more to line needles back on.
111826		11500		-6.6	Through some tops just reaching this level.
					End R6
		13000		-9.0	R7 still working cells on leading pt. of line.
112436		"			End 7 that had prec
		"		-8.22	Start 7.2 yellow radar along track.
—					End 7.2 N. Two vane problem, had to switch off
2hr		8500			
1186		"			target clouds - photo.
		"		-0.2	Start 8 cloud top ~ 1000 above.
—					In cloud, hearing precip.
					plates 2DC. 1 gm ³ lwc
114305		"			End 8
		10500		-4.1	R9 running near 11d to line of cells but will penetrate the end one, cloud top ~ 1000 above.
115011		12000		R10	try to hit best one so get just single cell glaciated initially.
				-6.6	

may be to left of target

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....

Date

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115203		12000		-9.7 at end	End 10 8 ms in R9
		13000		-10.9	with thin cloud top of 1st cell.
					2 cells, 2nd is higher & more glaciated.
115856		13000			End 11.1 many needles.
					Turb. probe was iced during that run.
120730		8500			Target clouds 2 photos, with run to cluster.
121022				-0.9	R12 tops to ~3000 above.
121152					End 12. ↓ to get more to
		10000		-3.45	R13 precip as later clouds.
					out of initial cells into some stratiform stuff.
121632		"			End 13
122051		11500		-5.9	R14 may be a diff cloud further to N but looks similar
					Precip on entry.
					press. supercooled rain.
122803		13000		-8.3	R15 skimming edge of cell to avoid bed.
					plenty precip in the cell.
123502		14000		-11.1	R16 maybe 2 cloud passes. 184/11 ms T
					1st is more growing.
					just turning in at start of close
1248..		8500			R17 alongwind initially
	aimed to 2Rin cell on R17				clouds all way back to base?
125140		9500		-1.8	R18 Top ~1000 above.
				-3 at end.	little precip initially.
					cell quite small & isolated.

1219
1h25
task

3h

4th
close

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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5th cloud

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125928		11000		-4.3	R19 went updrafts in last cloud pass.
					R20 descending through a cloud at least
		9500		-0.17	2nd cell OK.
130652					End R20 +6 ms ⁻¹
131029		10000		-3.0	R21 These were ice cells than lot 2 or 3 cloud cloud top ~ 1000 above.
					2 cells, sun lit. 3.5ms ⁻¹
					supercooled rain.
131714		11500		-5.4	R22 top risen rapidly
		? not much small ice?			will be skimming left to avoid req.
		13500		-8.6	R23 cell decaying rapidly.
132603		"			End R23 & Start P3 little or no updraft left.
132930					AMS open again for low level.
					Descent in a gap between clouds.
		3000			restart profile. low level leg will
				1001 QNH	be nicely downwind of work area.
13		250			End Profile.
134326		500			R24
					Profile shows some CIN but potential to give convection like we saw.
					Poss NTC recovery.
135329		500			End R24 / profile

4th

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B246

Date: 22/09/06 **Operator:** KFT **DRS Time:** 08:15:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 1**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:35:00	745	0.06	0			90.5										Heaters on FL	
09:38:00	872	0.35	0	1		11.5	750	0	0							1 FL080	
09:39:29	1080	0.06	15	2000	1000	0.50		0								1 FL100 noise on 2DC	
09:41:00	1362	0.06	40	2000		1		0								Noise on 2DC	
09:49:00	2464	0.06	208	5000	2000	26.50	750		100							10 FL100	
09:51:00	1395	0.06	269	0	0	39											
09:54:40	1545	0.05	270	8		7.5	550	1350	64							8	
09:56:00	1556	0.06	270	90		25.5	500	3083	64							8,11 FL160	
09:58:00	1863	0.06	271	70		2.5	700	41.67	64							8,11 FL160	
10:00:00	1536	0.06	271	2		1	700	175	64							8 FL160	
10:02:00	1436	0.06	271	8		2.5	700	283	64							8	
10:04:00	1505	0.05	271	10		4.5	425	766	64							8 FL160	
10:06:00	1572	0.06	272	100		51.5	675	12450	64							8 FL160	
10:08:00	1681	0.06	278	200		110	550	14241	500							8 FL160 START P1	
10:09:55	1379	0.06	279	0		0	0	0	0							FL150	
10:10:52	1308	0.06	283	200		73	775	5283	800							8 FL140	
10:12:00	1474	0.06	285	8		0	0	0	0							8 FL130	
10:12:55	1082	0.06	285	0		0	0	0	0							FL120	
10:13:50	1540	0.06	285	0		0	0	0	0							FL110	
10:14:50	1149	0.06	285	0		0	0	0	0							FL100	
10:15:50	995	0.06	285	8	0	0	0	0	0							FL090 HEATERS OFF	
10:16:50	926	0.06	285	2	0	0	0	0	0							FL080	
10:17:40	923	0.06	285	2	0	0	0	0	0							FL070	
10:19:01	963	0.06	285	2	0	0	0	0	0							FL060	
10:20:08	1001	0.06	285	10	0	0	0	0	0							FL050	
10:21:00	959	0.06	285	8	0	0	0	0	0							FL040 profile interrupted	
10:23:10	1033	0.06	285	10	0	0	0	0	0							FL040	
10:24:10	1115	0.06	285	10	0	0	0	0	0							FL030	
10:25:10	1120	0.06	285	10	0	0	0	0	0							FL020	
10:26:08	807	0.07	285	20	0	0	0	0	0							FL010	
10:26:50	1313	0.06	285	20	0	0	0	0	0							FL005 END P1	
10:28:46	877	0.06	285	20	1	0	0	0	0							START R1 AT 500FTASL	
10:30:00	679	0.06	285	20	0	0	0	0	0								
10:32:00	606	0.07	285	30	1	0	0	0	0								
10:35:00	736	0.07	285	30		0	0	0	0								
10:37:00	775	0.06	285	40		0	0	0	0								
10:39:00	1031	0.06	285	50		0	0	0	0							END R1	
10:39:23	1028	0.06	285	40		0	0	0	0							FL010	
10:40:05	960	0.06	285	70		0	0	0	0							START R2 500FT BELOW CLOUD BASE	
10:42:00	807	0.06	285	70		0	0	0	0								
10:45:00	879	0.06	285	100		0	0	0	0								
10:47:00	1097	0.06	285	20		0	0	0	0								
10:50:00	951	0.06	285	20		0	0	0	0							END R2 START P2	
10:50:34	842	0.06	285	40		0	0	0	0							FL020	
10:51:38	1024	0.06	285	10	1	0	0	0	0							FL030	
10:52:40	740	0.06	285	10		0	0	0	0							FL040	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B246

Date: 22/09/06	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:53:53	749	0.06	285	8		0	0	0	0							FL050	
10:54:48	646	0.06	285	8		0	0	0	0							FL060	
10:55:55	696	0.06	285	2		0	0	0	0							FL070	
10:56:50	811	0.06	285	5		0	0	0	0							FL080	
10:57:22	665	0.06	285	2		0	0	0	0							FL085 END P2	
11:00:00	912	0.06	285	3		0	0	0	0							HEATERS ON	
11:02:00	817	0.06	285	3		0	0	0	0								
11:03:16	1041	0.06	285	2		0	0	0	0							START R3	
11:04	2037	0.07	291	4000		364	325	16.67	800						1	CLOUD	
11:05:03	1066	0.06	509	3		0	0	0	0							END R3	
11:07:20	1083	0.06	509	1		0	0	0	0							FL095	
11:09:12	1014	0.05	509	0		0	0	0	0							START R4 AT FL095	
11:09:56	772	0.06	513	3000		174	175	1000	500						11, 1	CLOUD	
11:13:00	1009	0.06	729	2		0	0	0	0							FL100	
11:14:00	779	0.06	729	0		0	0	0	0							FL105	
11:14:44	739	0.06	729	0		0	0	0	0							START R5	
11:15:48	1253	0.10	749	8000		648	650	5074	3200						8,6,7	CLOUD	
11:17:50	1112	0.06	896	2		0	0	0	0							FL110	
11:18:29	1126	0.06	897	4000		276	725	44633	2500						8,6	CLOUD	
11:19:50			987	4000											8,7	CLOUD	
11:21:06	1026	0.06	987	10		1	800	108							4,8	FL120	
11:21:58	871	0.06	987	0		0	0	0	0							FL130 START R7.1	
11:23:40	13032	0.14	1009	8000		347	775	49633							6,8	CLOUD	
11:27:11	758	0.06	1017	0		0	0	0	0							START R7.2 AT FL130	
11:27:58	1925	0.13	1050	8000		500	800		3200						6,7,8	CLOUD	
11:29:08	1203	0.06	1065	8		1	600	400	2500						8	END R7.2	
11:34:27	785	0.06	1065	5		2.5	400	0	0						8,	FL070	
11:35:37	724	0.06	1065	2		0	0	0	0							FL080	
11:36:06	967	0.06	1065	3		0	0	0	0							FL085	
11:37:06	644	0.06	1065	2		0	0	0	0							START R8 AT FL085	
11:39:25	2291	0.12	1086	5000		370	775	5566	3200						8	CLOUD - ASPHERIC LARGE	
11:41:15	1144	0.06	1122	100		231	800	6250	6400						7,8		
11:43:13	811	0.05	1162	8		0	0	0	0							END R8	
11:44:20	1138	0.06	1162	2		0	0	0	0						8		
11:44:54	1140	0.06	1162	0		0	0	0	0							START R9 AT FL105	
11:46:50	4005	0.08	1194	8000		528	125	857							8	CLOUD - NOISE ON 2DP?	
11:47:56	1240	0.06	1237	0		0	0	0	0							END R9	
11:50:11	1103	0.06	1237	0		0	0	0	0							START R10 AT FL120	
11:50:45	2303	0.08	1241	4000		1762	550	49000	800						6,7,8	CLOUD	
11:52:05	1215	0.06	1334	2		0	0	0	0							END R10	
11:55:32	1026	0.06	1334	0		0	0	0	0							START R11 AT FL130	
11:57:30	1914	0.13	1347	2000		1780	725	87000	1200						5,6,8	CLOUD	
11:59:00	929	0.06	1364	0		0	0	0	0							END R11	
12:03:00	625	0.06	1365	0		0	0	0	0							FL110	
12:03:55	925	0.06	1364	1		0	0	0	0							FL100	
12:04:24	901	0.06	134	1		0	0	0	0							FL090	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B246

Date: 22/09/06	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 08:15:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:05:05	692	0.06	1364	1		0	0	0	0							FL080	
12:05:54	966	0.06	1364	8		0	0	0	0							FL070	
12:06:30	1148	0.06	1364	8		0	0	0	0							FL060	
12:07:08	934	0.06	1364	2				0	0						8	FL070	
12:08:00	799	0.06	1364	2		0	0	0	0							FL085	
12:10:33	620	0.05	1364	2		0	0	0	0							START R12 AT FL085	
12:11:00	1231	0.13	1380	2000		175	200	400	1600						8	CLOUD	
12:11:52	818	0.06	1400	5		0	0	0	0							END R12	
12:13:52	695	0.06	1400	2		0	0	0	0							START R AT FL100	
12:14:58	3900	0.08	1442	2000		500	275	7000	3200						8,1	CLOUD	
12:16:34	910	0.06	1469	2		21	490	0	0						5	END R13	
12:19:10	832	0.06	1469	100		50	800	3000	3200						8	FL115	
12:20:53	928	0.06	1470	2		0	0	0	0							START R AT FL115	
12:23:15	2762	0.11	1497	4000		1450	7000	7625	3200						5,8,1	CLOUD	
12:26:40	841	0.06	1539	0		0	0	0	0							FL130	
12:28:04	569	0.06	1539	0		0	0	0	0							START R12 AT FL130	
12:30:10	1476	0.14	1553	8000		2180	400	10966	2000						8	CLOUD	
12:34:00	894	0.15	1602	400		46.5	750	25000	200						8	'CLEAR' AIR	
12:35:02	900	0.06	1602	0		0	0	0	0							START R AT FL140	
12:36:40	1701	0.14	1607	2000		2114	550	67016	200						5,7,8	CLOUD FL140	
12:47:47	544	0.06	1623	5		0	0	0	0							START R17 AT FL085	
12:49:25	2106	0.12	1647	4000		156	250	1410	800						8	CLOUD	
12:50:10	936	0.06	1672	8		0	0	0	0							END R 17	
12:53:41	655	0.06	1672	2		0	0	0	0							START R18 AT FL095	
12:55:10	1530	0.13	1735	4000		198	450	1559	400						1,8	CLOUD	
12:59:30	705	0.05	1735	1		0	0	0	0							START R19 AT FL110	
13:01:20	1106	0.09	1744	3000		383	575	2583	800						8	CLOUD	
13:02:19	763	0.06	1765	0		0	0	0	0							END R19	
13:05:17	633	0.06	1773	2		0	0	0	0							START R20 AT FL085	
13:06:10	1880	0.15	1793	8000		489	150	1000	1000						8	CLOUD	
13:07:04	876	0.06	1811	2		0	0	0	0							END R20	
13:10:29	735	0.06	1811	1		0	0	0	0							START R21 AT FL100	
13:11:50	1590	0.12	1876	4000		700	600	5808	200						1,8	CLOUD	
13:17:19	798	0.06	1876	0		0	0	0	0							START R22 AT FL115 (NOISE ON 2DC)	
13:18:50	1463	0.14	1897	8000		1033	475	13500	475						1,8	CLOUD	
13:23:34	835	0.06	1928	0		0	0	0	0							START R23 AT FL135 (NOISE ON 2DC)	
13:25:15	1503	0.10	1931	2000		750	400	0	0						8,5	CLOUD	
13:26:40	1423	0.06	1931	0		0	0	0	0							FL130	
13:27:55	632	0.06	1931	0		0	0	0	0							FL120	
13:28:50	831	0.06	1931	0		800	400	2000	200						11,8	FL110	
13:31:30	730	0.06	1931	1			750	100	3200						8	FL090	
13:33:25	573	0.06	1931	1				8.33	3200							FL070	
13:34:30	827	0.06	1931	8		0	0	0	0							FL060	
13:35:27	892	0.06	1931	10		0	0	0	0							FL050	
13:36:33	913	0.06	1931	10		0	0	0	0							FL040	
13:37:24	745	0.06	1931	20		0	0	0	0							INTERRUPT 3000FT	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B246 T/O: 09:32:57
Date of Flight: 22/09/06 Land: 14:42:00

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	Y	52916 09-14
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		09-14
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	MFDB 090000 145000	NB Always use 0 and 240000 as times 657 BLOCKS
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	02062006 N	Note the calibration file used Total Glitches = 0 Sec File written ok? Y Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour PROCFSSP 21907 BLOCKS
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	Leads JW 20s	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	MFDC, MFDD	Note original and subsequent File sizes 317937
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	Not at 1 st pass	
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.	addt=1 (21s)	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B246

Date: 22/09/06

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	Downloaded from BADC 63204 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	304632 blocks
6) In PVWAVE		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	59985	Blocks read
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	59985	Blocks written
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	0	Bad reads
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat		
iii) exit		
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE		
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat		
d) Comment string:		Note times
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	T/O – 5 min	092500
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	Land + 5 min	145000
g) Read 2DC: Y		Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y		Vestigial error from tapes
i) Secondary data Y		
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	FRW,FSP,	Check FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA
k) cmd.str: Y	IMB,PCA,	And SEC files exist and have data
l) Auto time correction: N	SEC exist	
m) Full length secondary: N		
8) 2D image display and printing	Y	This must be done from Floods itself
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE	Images ok	Note any problems with images
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec	5	

Preparation of imagery for Core data product			Copy nos of pages to be produced
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10	093000 144200	10	Time to closest previous min
iv) exit PVWAVE	Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC	Y		Note files are ascii
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter			48pages 2DC, 45pages 2DP
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files			
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO			NB an error message may Appear, floating point Exception, rerun and use Time quoted in error Message, repeat until
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data 0 0 e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D		MFDD T/O + 30sec Land – 30sec 144130.3 2Dproc files present	Successful. 093330 144130 Note time data processed up to Check 2dproc files present 2dc, 2dp and dat
10) In PVWAVE			Error message about HDDR File should be ignored.
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!			
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'	12901, 178		Note records
iii) exit	10440		Note file size
11) MODIFY			
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		MFDD MFDE	
12) CHECKS:			
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	Y		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 246

Date: 19 September 2006

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann		Y	HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	N	
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red		Y	CVI	N	
“ IR		Y			
“ JO1D		Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer	Y	N
“ IR	N		Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D		Y	AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
MARSS	N		CDP		Y
DEIMOS	N		SAW	Y	N
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	N	N
SWS	N		2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS		N	Tube Sampling	Y	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B246

Date: 22 September 2006

Instruments

1. Core Chemistry – Nitrogen cylinder found to be empty pre-flight. Leak? Refilled then okay.
2. FFC – Picture very indistinct. Window suffered from sandblasting in Africa.
3. DFC – Camera struggling to cope with low light levels on initial profile descent, picture fading in and out between bright and dark.
4. Turb Probe – evidence of freezing on Sideslip Check parameter during initial transit. Iced up again at 1200Z and 1240Z, Sideslip and AOA and Pitot affected. Drop down to clear it.
5. Nevzorov – TWC Control Unit Alarm light flashing at 1129. Suspect winding broken, switch off TWC Control Unit. Tried to restart it several times over space of an hour but Alarm light flashing so switched off again. Tried again at low level, appears to be working now!

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls - Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 22/09/06

Flight No: 8246

Pre-Flighter: JT

<u>Item</u>	<u>✓ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	✓	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
		<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>		
2	✓	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	N ₂ NO GAS FILLED LABEL BY DA
3	✓	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	✓	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
5	✓	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
6	✓	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
7	✓	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	EXCEPT CO
8	x	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
9	✓	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	PROBLEMS, MODIUM OFFLINE - CORRUPT DISKS
10	✓	HORACE	Recording data	
11	✓	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
12	✓	HORACE	Status Checked	
13	✓	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
14	✓	Nevezorov	Checked and OFF	
15	✓	GPS	Checked	
16	✓	INU	Align	
17	✓	Cameras Pictures	Checked OK x 4	
18	✓	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	✓	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked	
20	✓	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	✓	GE	Balance checked	
22	✓	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
23	x	FWVS	Set up	NOT FITTED
24	✓	Satcom C	Turnaround message OK	
25	✓	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
26	✓	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	
27	x	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FITTED
28	✓	CGPS	Set up	VC DIA THIS TO MAKE RECORDS ASK
		<u>External</u>		
29	✓	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	✓	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	✓	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	✓	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	✓	Nevezorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	✓	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	✓	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	Cleaned
36	✓	Upper BBRs	Domes cleaned - Avalon	ASKED AVALON TO CLEAN, THEY DID
37	✓	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
38		Heimann	Lens checked OK	
39	x	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	NOT FITTED
40	✓	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	✓	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	✓	Tools	Avalon informed	

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B246:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	6 Oct 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Down/Forward Facing Cameras

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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